

TABLE 1—RESULT OF ANALYSES

Metal-nicotinamide complexes Molecular formula	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	%C	%H	%N	%Cl	Δm in ohm^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
1. $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N.CONH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	Yellow	340	84.68 *(84.19)	3.00 (2.87)	13.17 (13.29)	16.81 (16.82)	8.2
2. $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N.CONH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	Light pink	320	28.00 (28.25)	2.86 (2.37)	10.54 (10.89)	14.5 (18.90)	6.8
<i>Metal-brucine complexes</i>							
1. $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	Black	215	48.91 (48.32)	5.01 (4.58)	4.93 (4.90)	11.95 (12.40)	18.1
2. $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	Light pink	270	42.80 (41.88)	4.32 (3.96)	4.20 (4.24)	10.94 (10.74)	34.0
3. $\text{Os}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Black	above 360	38.00 (38.03)	4.21 (3.61)	3.74 (3.86)	19.96 (19.52)	86.6
4. $\text{Ir}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Dirty white	"	35.97 (37.92)	3.88 (3.60)	3.81 (3.85)	20.03 (19.47)	27.6
5. $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}_4$	Reddish brown	"	34.45 (33.98)	3.80 (3.22)	3.42 (3.45)	25.74 (26.16)	17.0

* Calculated values are given in parentheses.

insoluble in water and common organic solvents but slightly soluble in DMF and THF. The molar conductivity measurements carried out in DMSO indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The ir spectrum of brucine shows two bands at 1655 and 1395 cm^{-1} , which are respectively assigned to CO and CN stretching vibrations of the acylazole system³. The CO stretching band is lowered by 10 to 20 cm^{-1} in the complexes and it favours the possibility of coordination through oxygen of the carbonyl group. The strong intensity band at 1115 cm^{-1} in the brucine has been assigned to CO stretching of the seven membered cyclic ether^{3,4}, which shows a slight lowering of frequency in all the complexes except Rh(III) complex where the lowering is quite marked. It is therefore assumed that the second Rh atom coordinates through this oxygen.

On the basis of the ir evidence it may be inferred that Pt(II), Pd(II), Os(IV), Rh(III) and Ir(IV) coordinate through the carbonyl groups of the acylazole ring. The complexes of iridium and rhodium with brucine are found to be diamagnetic.

The thermogram of palladium nicotinamide complex shows a wt. loss of 10.0% at 200° which may be the elimination of CONH₂ group (theo. wt. loss is 10.44%). A break in the curve occurs at 30.0% wt. loss at 356°. This may be the elimination of C₈H₄N of the nicotinamide and from which CONH₂ was given off (theo. wt. loss=28.95%). After this, there is a continuous weight loss which may entail the elimination of the second molecule of nicotinamide, sublimation of complex species and the removal of the chloride ions. The weight becomes constant at 81.0% wt. loss at 460° which is more than that calculated for the formation of metallic palladium (74.75%).

The thermogram of platinum brucine complex shows an inflection point at 20.0% wt. loss and 160-200° temperature. This may be due to the elimination of the two OCH₃ groups and the (CH₂)₃N

which accounts for 17.86% wt. loss. The maximum weight loss is 73.0% at 380°, which accounts for the formation of metallic platinum (theo. wt. loss=70.44%). The rhodium complex shows inflection points at 280 and 400° with wt. losses of 52.0% (theo. wt. loss for the formation of 2 RhCl₃=48.47%) and 80.0% (theo. wt. loss for the formation of 2 Rh=87.34%). These thermograms indicate the removal of two methoxy groups and the CH₂-CH₂-N-CH₂ of the aliphatic pyrrocoline ring at low temperatures when nothing else is eliminated. This may mean the non-coordination of the metal ion with this nitrogen in all these complexes as also evidenced by ir spectra.

The electronic spectra of Ir (Brucine) Cl₄ shows bands at 17391, 20833 and 25000 cm^{-1} . This may have a pentacoordinate square pyramidal structure and the first and the last band may be due to $d_{z^2} \leftarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz}/d_{yz} \leftarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions.

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Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Complexes at Different Ionic Strengths

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THE role of electrolytes on the dissociation constants of ligands and their complexes are not well-understood. The dissociation constants are

generally determined in presence of large excess of neutral electrolyte. But in view of the present knowledge of solvent structure and the structure-breaking effect of electrolytes, changed dielectric constant, increased ion-pair formation etc, it is desirable to throw light on the effects of different "neutral electrolytes" on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes. Unfortunately systematic efforts to explore the role of "neutral electrolytes" on the dissociation constants of ligands and their complexes are lacking. In view of the extremely limited or no knowledge of the activities of different constituents for the reaction

the thermodynamic equilibrium or dissociation constants are difficult to determine. In a previous communication¹ we outlined the usual procedures to determine the thermodynamic equilibrium or dissociation constants and the difficulties associated with them.

Furthermore, the solvent was previously believed to be an inert medium to carry out the reactions. The impact of solute-solvent interactions are known relatively recently. A number of different types of solute-solvent interactions are known². The relative magnitude of the different types of interactions are difficult to estimate.

These interactions may reinforce or cancel each other making the real understanding extremely difficult.

In addition to the complexing capability of different ions of the neutral electrolytes with the ions of the reacting systems, the increased knowledge of ion-solvent interactions have pointed to a number of limitations particularly when the ionic strengths are high.

These are :

1. In presence of large excess of neutral electrolytes, polarization of the solvent (water) molecule and variation of microscopic and macroscopic dielectric constant³⁻⁵ take place.
2. Different electrolytes change the activity coefficients of uncharged electrolytes to different extents⁶.
3. There is a breakdown of the tetrahedral structure of water in presence of ions⁷. Ion solvation leads to a decrease in the effective concentration of solvent molecules particularly in presence of high concentration of electrolyte^{8,9}. Solvation of different ions are also different.
4. Ion-association leads to the reduction of ionic-strength¹⁰. It is thus imperative to determine the dissociation constants of ligands and their complexes at different ionic strengths using different electrolytes and explore the role of "neutral electrolytes" and various factors associated with

them affecting the equilibrium or dissociation constants. With these objects in view, we determined the equilibrium constants for the following reactions :

Where B = either 2,2' → -dipyridyl, or
1,10 → -phenanthroline

in presence of "neutral electrolyte" KCl at different ionic strengths (0.03, 0.05, 0.08, 0.10, 0.20, 0.50, 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0M respectively). The results are described in the present communication.

Experimental

The experimental details are the same as given in our previous communications¹¹⁻¹³. Only the experiments were done in presence of KCl (G.R.E.M.) of different concentrations. The dissociation constants for the reaction (1) at different ionic strengths have been taken from our earlier works¹. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Discussions

All the reactions are "isoelectronic" in nature and therefore, it is expected that the ionic strength should not change the *pK*-values to a considerable extent. In case of reaction (1), the change in *pK*-values is only marginal at low ionic strengths but considerable change occurs at high ionic strengths. The trend of the *pK*-values for the reaction (2) is found to be inconsistent. Errors in *pK*-values would be considerable due to slight error in the calculation of the concentrations of either H⁺ ion or BH⁺ ion. It will be apparent from the values for *pK* for reaction (2) in case of dipyridyl complex¹². The values are 4.12 (using observed hydrogen ion concentration after proper correction) and 4.37 (using calculated H⁺ ion concentration) at low ionic strengths.

Kolthoff¹⁴ *et al*'s result showed a variation of concentration equilibrium constant *K_c* (for 2) in case of *tris*-ferrous phenanthroline complex from 9.7×10^{-7} at low ionic strengths to 39×10^{-7} at high ionic strengths whereas the activity equilibrium constant reported is the average of values varying from 8.4×10^{-7} to 1.8×10^{-7} . The activity equilibrium constants have been calculated using the activity coefficients of PhH⁺ which they determined from *pH*-measurements of 1:1 mixture of Ph and PhH⁺ in varying concentrations of KCl. The results have been analysed in a previous work¹¹.

The *pK*-values presented for reaction (1) cannot be regarded as true concentration quotients as the H⁺ ion concentrations used to calculate the *pK*-values refer to *a_{H+}* whereas the concentrations (BH⁺) and (B) are determined spectrophotometrically, the *f_{BH+}* values are unknown.

Moreover, the liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude which increased with increase in

TABLE 1

Temperature = 25°

Ionic Strength (μ)/mol lit ⁻¹	pK-values for the reaction $\text{PhH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Ph} + \text{H}^+$	Extinction coefficient values of the complex FePh_3^{2+}			pK-values for the reaction $\text{FePh}_3^{2+} + 3\text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{3+} + 3\text{PhH}^+$	pK-values for the reaction $\text{FePh}_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{3+} + 3\text{Ph}$
		nm 400	nm 510	nm 520		
0.03	5.11	11840	11700	11190	5.48	20.81
0.05	5.15	10960	11150	10025	4.60	20.05
0.08	5.13	11413	11913	11270	4.57	20.26
0.10	5.12	11380	11610	10750	5.65	21.01
0.50	5.23	10910	11170	10287	5.56	21.25
0.50	5.28	10970	11233	10377	5.59	21.45
1.00	5.30	10960	11202	10360	4.99	20.89
2.00	5.39	11042	11365	10592	4.77	20.94
3.00	5.49	10865	11217	10557	5.04	21.51

TABLE 2

Temperature = 25°

Ionic Strength (μ)/mol lit ⁻¹	pK-values for the reaction $\text{DipyH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Dipy} + \text{H}^+$	Extinction coefficient values of the complex FeDipy_3^{2+}			pK-values for the reaction $\text{FeDipy}_3^{2+} + 3\text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{3+} + 3\text{DipyH}^+$	pK-values for the reaction $\text{FeDipy}_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{3+} + 3\text{Dipy}$
		nm 400	nm 510	nm 520		
0.03	4.61	8404	8364	7688	2.73	16.66
0.05	4.63	8468	8396	8068	2.74	16.63
0.08	4.63	8563	8514	8004	2.79	16.68
0.10	4.75	8650	8594	8100	2.59	16.84
0.20	4.75	7999	7961	7685	2.97	17.22
0.50	4.82	7918	7882	7554	3.06	17.52
1.00	5.32	8311	8256	7961	2.55	18.51
2.00	5.45	8289	8250	8093	2.53	18.88
3.00	5.61	8482	8467	8325	2.38	19.21

salt-concentration limits the accuracy of the determination of the a_{H^+} . Thus the determination of either concentration or thermodynamic stability constant are extremely difficult. Calculated values of H^+ ion concentration may give erroneous values of BH^+ from (1), slight error in C_{H^+} or C_{BH^+} would mean a large change in pK-values for reaction (2). The activities of different ions change differently and in an anomalous way with ionic strengths. The resultant effects of (1) and (2) would be reflected in (3).

The effect of ionic strength on ϵ is not clear and consistent. No regular trend is observed. However, considerable increase in pK-values for reactions (1) and (3) are observed in case of 2,2'-dipyridyl compared to 1,10-phenanthroline at high ionic strengths. The greater stability of 1,10-phenanthroline is known to be due to greater resonance stabilization and fixed coplanarity of 1,10-phenanthroline compared to 2,2'-dipyridyl. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that at higher ionic strengths in presence of structured solvent environments due to considerable 'electrostriction', the free-rotation of 2,2'-dipyridyl may be restricted leading to greater coplanarity and consequent increase in pK-values¹.

However, quantitative knowledge of (i) ion-pair formation, (ii) change in static dielectric constant values, (iii) solvation and (iv) particularly the activity coefficient values of different ions in addition to the knowledge of the dissociation constants of

different reactions at various ionic strengths are needed to understand the role of "neutral electrolytes" on the dissociation constants.

For ordinary purposes, it is desirable to determine the dissociation constants at low ionic strengths to get the thermodynamic values relatively free from errors discussed above.

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Chromium(III) Mixed Chelates containing 2-(2'-Pyridyl) Benzimidazole

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2-(2'-PYRIDYL) benzimidazole (PBzH)¹⁻⁴ can function as a neutral bidentate NN donor(I) and as a monobasic bidentate NN donor(II). Reaction

of this ligand with $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6]$ gives a mixed ligand complex⁵ $[Cr(PBzH)(NCS)_2(OH)(OH_2)] 1.5 C_2H_5OH$. Binuclear halobridged complexes of the type $[Cr(PBz)_2X]_2$ ($X = Cl, Br$) have also been reported⁴. We report three new mixed ligand complexes $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$, $[Cr(PBz)(o\text{-phen})(tu)_2]Cl_2$ and $[Cr(PBz)_2(dipy)(tu)_2]Cl_2$ ($BigH =$ biguanide; $dipy = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl; $o\text{-phen} = o$ -phenanthroline and $tu =$ thiourea). In all the three cases the benzimidazole behaves as a monobasic bidentate NN donor.

Experimental

Tris(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride and trichloro *tris*(thiourea) chromium(III) chloride were obtained by published procedures^{5,6}. 2-(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazole was obtained by a modified procedure described by Ghosh and Mishra⁷.

Synthesis of $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$: 0.9 gm of *tris*(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride was dissolved in hot water. A solution of 0.4 gm of the ligand (PBzH) in alcohol was added to the above solution and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hrs. After filtration the solution was reduced to a small volume and was allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator. The crude material was purified from alcohol.

Syntheses of $[Cr(PBz)(o\text{-phen/dipy})(tu)_2]Cl_2$: An alcoholic solution of 1 gm of *o*-phenanthroline (or of 0.8 gm of dipyrldyl) was added to a 1:1 alcoholic solution of 1 gm of $[Cr(tu)_2Cl_2]$. On refluxing for 2 hrs the colour of the solution changed from green to red. About 0.5 gm of PBzH ligand (dissolved in alcohol) was added and the solution refluxed for 10 hrs. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was taken almost to dryness. The pasty mass was taken up in alcohol, concentrated under a fan and allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator.

Results and Discussion

We had earlier shown⁸ that *o*-phenanthroline or α, α' -dipyridyl reacts with *tris*(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride to furnish mixed chelates $[Cr(o\text{-phen/dipy})(BigH)_2]Cl_2$. With 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole a different type of product, $[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl$, is obtained. Its conductivity ($\Lambda_M = 110 \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) in methanol indicates a 1:1 electrolytic nature. The magnetic moment ($\mu = 3.7 \text{ B.M.}$) is as expected of a $3d^3$ ion complex. The electronic spectra of the complex reveal a band around 18.2 kK (= 10 Dq), which is assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition. The 10 Dq value is, however, lower than those⁹ observed for several other $[CrN_6]$ complexes e.g.:

$[Cr(BigH)_2]^{3+}$ (20.7 kK); $[Cr(en)_3]^{3+}$ (21.8 kK); $[Cr(NH_2)_6]^{3+}$ (21.5 kK). Deprotonated 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole thus appears to be a weaker ligand compared to BigH, en, NH_2 .

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF CHROMIUM(III) MIXED CHELATES

Chelate	Colour	Analyses(%)				H ₂ O	Λ_M^{**}	μ (B.M.)	10 Dq (kK)
		Cr	N	Cl	S				
$[Cr(PBz)_2(BigH)]Cl 1.5H_2O$	Brick red	8.8 (8.6)*	25.2 (25.4)	6.2 (5.8)	—	4.4 (4.4)	105	3.70	18.2
$[Cr(o\text{-phen})(PBz)(tu)_2]Cl_2$	Dirty green	7.7 (8.0)	19.5 (19.8)	11.0 (10.9)	10.0 (9.8)	—	154	3.65	17.1
$[Cr(dipy)(PBz)(tu)_2]Cl_2$	Brown	8.0 (8.3)	19.2 (20.1)	11.2 (11.9)	10.5 (10.2)	—	158	3.80	—

* Calculated values are given in parentheses.

** In methanol at $10^{-2} - 10^{-4} M$; $\text{ohms}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$.